

Physical Properties of some Mono- and Di-alkyl-substituted Amides at Different Temperatures

Ram Gopal and S. A. Rizvi

Properties like density, viscosity, and surface tension of some mono- and di-alkyl-substituted aliphatic amides have been determined at different temperatures within 30-90° range. The absolute critical temperatures, as estimated from the density data, for the mono-substituted compounds are higher than those for the di-substituted ones although the surface tensions of all of them are of the same order ($\approx 25-30$ dynes/cm).

Alkyl-substituted aliphatic amides have attracted attention of a number of workers in recent years for their having a strong hydrogen-bonding property. Although their dipole moments and dielectric constants¹⁻², association, and hydrogen bonding¹⁻² have been widely studied, a systematic study of their common physical properties like density, viscosity, and surface tension does not appear to have received the same attention; only disconnected accounts of viscosity and density have been reported at a few temperatures^{1,3,4} in some cases. These solvents are being used in this laboratory in connection with other research programmes and reference has to be often made to their properties. The present communication reports the density, viscosity, and surface tension of *N*-methylformamide (NMF), *N*-methylacetamide (NMA), *N*-methylpropionamide (NMP), *NN*-dimethylformamide (DMF), *NN*-diethylformamide (DEF), and *NN*-dimethylacetamide (DMA) at different temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Available samples of the liquids were treated with freshly ignited quicklime and were distilled under reduced pressure, the middle fractions having been collected for redistillation. The process was repeated till the electrical conductance of the distillate, in each case, fell to about 10^{-5} to 10^{-6} mho. This was stored in a dark-coloured amber bottle in a dry nitrogen box and used, as far as possible, immediately after distillation. All possible precautions were taken to exclude atmospheric moisture during the course of experiments. An oil thermostat was used for making measurements and its accuracy at lower temperatures was $\pm 0.05^\circ$ and at higher temperatures, $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The use of oil in the thermostat, in place of the customary water, avoids the presence of water vapour surrounding the measuring apparatus and at the same time it helps to attain the higher temperatures without much evaporation.

* Work supported by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, India.

1. Lender and Gormley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5731.
2. Bass *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 503, 509.
3. Dawson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 1986; 1957, 79, 288, 4662.
4. Thomas and Hoover, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 874, Lester *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, 60, 1076; Franch and Glover, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, 51, 1420; Sinykov *et al.*, *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 56, 962a.

Density was determined with the help of a dilatometer, graduated in 0.01 ml and could be read with ease to 0.005 ml. Viscosity was determined in an Ostwald type viscometer, slightly modified to exclude moisture⁵. Surface tension was measured with a modified drop-weight method similar to that of Krishna and Venkateswarlu⁶. The outer radius of the nozzle was 0.249 cm and the pipette was graduated in 0.001 ml. The surface tension, σ , was calculated from the expression:

$$\sigma = \frac{Vd g (F)}{r} \text{ dynes/cm}$$

where V is the average volume of a drop; d , the density of the liquid at the temperature concerned and r , the outer radius of the nozzle (*i.e.* 0.249 cm); g , acceleration due to gravity, and (F) is a function of V/r^3 . The values of (F) were taken from the Table of Harkins and Brown⁷ for the different values of V/r^3 . The accuracy of the apparatus was checked with benzene and water at 40° and 50°. The values of σ , obtained experimentally in these cases, agreed within very close limits with those recorded in the literature.

TABLE I

Compound.	Temperature							
	30°.	40°.	50°.	60°.	70°.	80°.	90°.	
Amide.								
	d	0.9950	0.9860	0.9782	0.9704	0.9610	0.9517	0.9420
	η	0.0156	0.0133	0.01166	0.01012	0.00873	0.00774	0.0069
	σ	37.99	36.50	35.02	33.57	32.49	31.32	29.99
NMA	d	0.9498	0.9415	0.9332	0.9262	0.9180	0.9096	0.9016
	η	0.0389	0.0304	0.0245	0.01976	0.01614	0.0135	0.0112
	σ	33.97	32.17	30.62	29.41	28.27	27.31	26.35
NMP	d	0.9260	0.9182	0.9107	0.9028	0.8950	0.8860	0.8790
	η	0.0456	0.0358	0.0284	0.0225	0.0184	0.0140	0.0117
	σ	31.20	30.11	29.12	28.40	27.95	27.25	26.84
DMF	d	0.9412	0.9310	0.9211	0.9116	0.9022	0.8916	0.8820
	η	0.00737	0.00682	0.00627	0.00572	0.00517	0.00478	0.00422
	σ	33.10	32.02	30.94	29.97	28.90	27.87	26.83
DEF	d	0.8980	0.8896	0.8808	0.8722	0.8636	0.8539	0.8447
	η	0.01076	0.00966	0.00855	0.00748	0.00653	0.00583	..
	σ	27.65	26.90	26.11	25.12	24.34	23.56	22.82
DMA	d	0.9323	0.9232	0.9142	0.9054	0.8960	0.8872	0.8770
	η	0.00838	0.00786	0.00739	0.00680	0.00542	0.00483	0.0043
	σ	32.43	30.92	29.50	28.30	27.17	25.74	24.62

N.B.—density, d , expressed in g./ml, η in poise, and σ in dynes/cm.

DISCUSSION

The results recorded in Table I lead to the following general conclusions.

5. Tamm and Fuoss, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 67, 1943.

6. This *Journal*, 1958, 36, 804.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 499.

Viscosity.—All the liquids have high values of viscosity, indicating strong molecular interaction leading to association. The viscosity decreases with rise in temperature. The mono-substituted amides are more viscous than the di-substituted ones, indicating weaker molecular interaction in the latter. The plot of $\log \eta$ against $1/T$ is found to be almost a straight line in every case within the temperature range investigated. The value of the activation energy of the viscous flow, E_{vis} , for different liquids, obtained from the slope of the $\log \eta - 1/T$ curve, is shown in Table II. It may be observed that E_{vis} for monoalkyl-substituted liquids are 3.4 kcal./mole and for dialkyl ones, 2.3 kcal./mole. These values slowly fall with rise in temperature. The values of E_{vis} for two types of liquids indicate higher molecular interaction in the mono-substituted compounds as compared to that in the di-substituted ones.

Surface Tension.—Surface tensions of both di- and mono-alkyl-substituted aliphatic amides are of the same order as can be seen from Table I. As usual, the surface tension decreases with increase in temperature and if the Ramsay-Eötvös-Shields constant for these liquids is calculated, it is found to decrease with rise in temperature, as happens in some other liquids⁸. Hence it is not possible to calculate either the molecular association or the critical temperature with the help of the Ramsay-Eötvös-Shields equation in these liquids. The absolute critical temperature can, however, be estimated with the help of the equation :

$$T_c = \frac{\Delta T}{(d_1/d_2)^{1/3} - 1} + T_2 + 6$$

proposed by Smith and co-workers⁹ and has been found to hold good satisfactorily for over seventy five liquids of different types. In this equation d_1 and d_2 are the densities at the absolute temperatures T_1 and T_2 ; T_c is the absolute critical temperature and $\Delta T = T_2 - T_1$. The values of T_c , thus obtained, are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Amide.	T_c .	* E_{vap} .	* W_c .	* E_{vis} .
NMF	675° K	11.1	2.6	3.1
NMA	690°	11.6	2.7	4.1
NMP	685°	11.5	2.5	4.5
DMF	624°	9.6	2.4	2.4
DEF	633°	10.2	2.6	3.0
DMA	637°	10.1	2.6	2.6

*These values correspond to 40° and expressed in kcal./mole.

It is obvious from Table II that the values of T_c for the monoalkyl-substituted liquids are higher ($\approx 685^\circ\text{K}$) than those ($\approx 625^\circ\text{K}$) for the di-substituted ones. Since the critical temperature may be taken as a rough measure of the interaction energies, the molecular interaction is stronger in the former than that in the latter.

Following Grunberg and Nissau¹⁰, some indirect evidence from the derived properties like work of cohesion, W_c , internal energy of vaporisation, ΔE_{vap} , and the activation

8. Partington, "Advanced Treatise on Physical Chemistry", Vol. II, Longmans Green & Co. London, 1951, p. 162.

9. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 443.

10. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, 45, 132.

energy of the viscous flow, $E_{vis.}$, for stronger interaction in the monoalkyl-substituted aliphatic amides than that in the di-substituted ones, can be offered. W_0 is given by:

$$W_0 = 2 \sigma N^{1/3} V_m^{2/3}$$

σ being the surface energy in cal./unit area; N , the Avogadro number, and V_m , the molar volume. Further, the internal energy of vaporisation¹¹ is given by

$$\Delta E_{vap.} = \Delta H_v - RT$$

ΔH_v , the normal enthalpy of vaporisation, can be estimated approximately from the expression¹²: $\Delta H_v \times \alpha = 10 \text{ kcal.}$, α being the coefficient of thermal expansion. This expression has been found to hold good for a large number of van der Waals liquids. The values of W_0 , $\Delta E_{vap.}$, obtained from the above expressions, and $E_{vis.}$, from $\log \eta - 1/T$ curves, at 40° are recorded in Table II.

It may be observed from Table II that for NMF, NMA and NMP, $E_{vis.}$ is greater than W_0 , whereas for DMF, DMA and DEF, both are of the same order, indicating that the former have a larger molecular interaction and association than the latter¹⁰. The association appears to increase in the order: NMP > NMA > NMF, as has been concluded by Leader and Gormley¹ from dielectric constant measurements. Since for the di-substituted amides $E_{vis.}$ and W_0 are very nearly identical, these behave as a normal liquid¹⁰. The same behaviour is indicated by the larger values of $\Delta E_{vap.}$ for the mono-substituted compounds ($\Delta E_{vap.} \approx 10-11 \text{ kcal.}$) than those for the di-substituted amides ($\Delta E_{vap.} \approx 9-10 \text{ kcal.}$).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW,

Received September 17, 1965,

11. Glasstone, Laidler, and Eyring, "The Theory of Rate Process", McGraw Hill Book Co., New York, 1941, p. 477.

12. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, 17, 1274.